

Speculation on Quantum Spin, Intrinsic Force and Special Relativity

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In previous notes, we presented a simple argument for obtaining the quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. We suggested that there are situations for which one cannot predict the outcome of an elastic collision and that given initial e_1, e_2 (energies) and p_1, p_2 (momentum vectors in 1-direction for simplicity), any e_i, e_j and p_i, p_j which conserve energy and momentum have the same product probability. Even in Newtonian elastic collisions of free particles, one sees calculations which allow any outcome which conserves momentum and energy. If the probability has the same real value for any free particle as no variable is being distributed and one wishes to impose Lorentz invariance, then $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ represent the probabilities.

This automatically gives rise to units in time and space, \hbar/E and \hbar/p (the \hbar comes from considerations linked to a photon). One may ask, however: What is the real physics behind dx and dt ? We argued in (1) that this physics is associated with force, in particular an intrinsic force. We considered a particle with rest mass m_0 and argued that this rest mass represents intrinsic force as it is proportional to Newton's inertia and the force needed to set it in motion. If viewed from a moving frame, $(0, m_0 c c)$ maps to (E, p) with E containing the intrinsic inertial force as well as enhancements due to motion and p containing the intrinsic m_0 as well as the velocity vector. For a particle with rest mass, we suggest that a key idea is this notion of intrinsic force. We argued that one may consider the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px = -m_0 c c t_1$ and introduce $dx=\hbar/E$, $dt=\hbar/p$, $dt_1=\hbar/(m_0 c c)$ and $dx \rightarrow \infty$ as $p \rightarrow 0$. This leads to $-E dt + p dx = 0$ or $-E/dx + p/dt = 0$. We then argued in (1) that p/dt is like an average force and from this we introduced $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Thus, dt and dx are linked with the notion of an average force.

We suggest that this notion of intrinsic force is the reason behind linearizing $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0 c c c c$ ((1)). $-E dt + p dx = 0$ is too simple to show the geometry linked with rotational invariance etc in ((1)), yet at the same time ((1)) is not linear in the intrinsic force m_0 . This is the physical reason why ((1)) should be linearized via Dirac's process, giving rise to spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

As a result, we postulate that a particle has an intrinsic force, in this case rest mass, which is directly linked with the probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and that one should be able to write an equation containing operators and the intrinsic force (in linear form) which also shows geometry. It is this equation which gives rise to spin.

At this point, this is a postulate, i.e. speculation. It would be good if one could find an example in which these ideas arise naturally, i.e. a case in which one did not have to linearize an equation like ((1)) or make special arguments in order to obtain $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. In that case, an equation linear in the intrinsic force would exist a priori and a direct link to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ would also naturally exist. We suggest that such an example does exist, namely for a photon. One may use the special relativistic equations developed for a particle with rest mass and set $m_0=0$ to obtain $E=[p] c$ for a photon. This is a fine equation, but unlike the rest mass case m_0 (proportional to the intrinsic force), there is no rest mass and no intrinsic force present for the photon. Certainly p (momentum) is linked with a force as both a particle with rest mass and a photon impart an impulse on a target, but momentum is not an intrinsic force, it is a consequential one. In the case of a rest mass, it arises because the rest mass (the intrinsic force) is seen to be moving. For a photon, one would then expect the existence of an intrinsic

force which gives rise to momentum. We suggest that the electric field (together with the magnetic) represents this intrinsic force and that Maxwell's equations allow one to directly write a linear equation in E (electric field) (no linearization required) which shows the geometry in the system. One may also explicitly show that E behaves as $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ if one extends $\cos(-Et+ipx)$ to a more general complex number. In other words, the postulates made for the particle with rest mass m_0 seem to naturally arise in the case of the photon. This, we argue, is why the procedures for finding spin for a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle with rest mass m_0 and a photon are so different even though both a photon and rest mass particle satisfy special relativity and are associated with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. It is the difference in the intrinsic force which is the key to finding spin, we speculate.

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ From Elastic Scattering Arguments

In previous notes, we argued that in some elastic scattering scenarios (perhaps tiny length scales or even Newtonian scales with point particles), one cannot deterministically know the outcome. One only knows that momentum and energy are conserved. This means that given an initial e_1, e_2 (energy) and p_1, p_2 (momentum vectors in 1D for simplicity), any e_i, e_j and p_i, p_j which conserve energy and momentum should have the same product probability. Furthermore, this probability cannot have differing real values because all free particles are on the same footing in the sense that there is no variable being distributed among them as total energy is in an ideal gas. Finally, if one wishes the result to be Lorentz invariant, one has:

$$\exp(-iEt)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Such a result is implicitly linked with the notion of force for a particle with rest mass in that one has forces in an elastic collision, but ((2)) should hold for two photons, i.e. the product of probabilities $p(E_1)p(E_2)=p(E_1+E_2)$ and a similar expression for p_1, p_2 without any notion of a collision or force.

From ((2)), one sees that there are distinct dt and dx units:

$$dt = \hbar/E \text{ and } dx = \hbar/p \quad ((3))$$

(Here \hbar arises from photon considerations which we have examined elsewhere.)

One might ask: What is the physical relevance of dt and dx ? In (1), we suggested that these are associated with an average force.

The Notion of Intrinsic Force For a Particle with Rest Mass

In (1), we suggested that given the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px = -m_0 c^2 t_1 \quad ((4))$$

One could view this in terms of an average force if one uses ((3)) and $dt_1 = \hbar/(m_0 c^2)$. In other words:

$$0 = -E dt + p dx = -m_0 c^2 dt + (p=0) * (dx \rightarrow \infty) \quad ((5))$$

For $-E dt + p dx$ one may divide by dt yielding $-E/dx + p/dt = 0 \quad ((6))$

We argue that p/dt and E/dx are average forces. Thus, the quantum ((3)) is really associated with the notion of forces and furthermore an intrinsic force m_0 (associated with inertia) is present in ((4)). We then suggest that when studying a particle, one wishes to have an equation linear in the intrinsic force (here m_0 =inertia), have an association with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and also see the geometry of the system. Based on these considerations, we suggest taking the Lorentz invariant:

$$-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0 \quad (c=1) \quad ((7))$$

and linearizing it as Dirac did. This involves writing $p \cdot A = p_i \cdot A_i$, where A_i is a 4x4 matrix. E and m_0 are also multiplied by matrices. These act on a vector and one calls this scenario spin $\frac{1}{2}$ and suggests it is linked to some kind of circular motion as it is known that electrons intrinsically interact with a magnetic field. Thus, there seems to be an intrinsic force related quantity beyond m_0 , namely spin.

We postulate:

((8a)) An object is associated with an intrinsic force. It is this force which ultimately gives rise to momentum which is a consequential force. In the rest mass case, m_0 is the intrinsic force as it is linked with inertial force. There is no momentum unless m_0 exists. P follows from the existence of m_0 .

((8b)) There is a consequential probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but this must appear in an equation containing the intrinsic force in a linear form. This is why Dirac linearized $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$, we argue. Given that such an equation, linear in the intrinsic force, may exhibit symmetries (rotational and others) in space, a matrix operator in addition to $-i\text{grad}$ for p and $i\partial/dt$ for E appear. This, in turn, leads to the existence of spin.

((8)) is a postulate or speculation. In the case of a rest mass m_0 , the ideas of ((8)) had to be imposed in order to first find $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and then to use it in a linearized form of $-EE + p \cdot p = -m_0 m_0$, with $E \rightarrow i\partial/dt$ and $p \rightarrow -i\text{grad}$.

We suggest that it would be good if the ideas of ((8)) appeared naturally in a particular example, We argue that they do in the case of a photon.

Photon Spin and Intrinsic Force

It is possible to consider special relativistic equations for a particle with rest mass. In particular, one has the Lorentz invariants:

$$-E\dot{E} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{p}} = -m_0 \dot{m}_0 \quad (c=1) \quad \text{and} \quad -E\dot{t} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} = -m_0 c \dot{t} \quad ((9))$$

One may formally set $m_0=0$ to obtain $E = |\mathbf{p}|$ (square root of the modulus) and $-E\dot{t} + \mathbf{p} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} = 0$, one dimension. In this situation, $m_0=0$ means that the intrinsic force discussed in ((8)) disappears. There is no m_0 and hence no inertia for a photon in this case. \mathbf{P} (momentum) was argued to be a consequential force. According to the postulate ((8)), one must find an intrinsic force (which creates the consequential force \mathbf{p}) for a photon and use it in a linear equation. Furthermore, this intrinsic force must be associated with $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$. At first this seems difficult, but we argue that Maxwell's electromagnetic equations directly give the results of ((8)) directly, without any efforts needed to create $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$ or linearize the first equation of ((9)).

We suggest that the intrinsic force in the case of the photon is the electric field $E\mathbf{i}$. In particular, Maxwell showed, using his equations, that light consists of an electric field perpendicular to a magnetic field in a plane, both following $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ and both perpendicular to the direction of motion. One may generalize $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ to $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$ (and show explicitly that $\hbar\omega = E$ and $\hbar k = \mathbf{p}$) and so the quantum mechanical $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$ is naturally associated with the intrinsic force $E\mathbf{i}$. Furthermore, one may show explicitly that momentum is created from the intrinsic force because:

$$\text{Momentum density} = 1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} \quad \text{where } \mathbf{B} \text{ is the magnetic field } ((10))$$

The only requirement left is to find a linear equation in the intrinsic force $E\mathbf{i}$ which shows spatial geometry and is linked to $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$. This latter link already exists due to ((10)). We argue Maxwell's equations without sources yield the required result.

$$\text{Grad} \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad \text{grad} \cdot \mathbf{E} = 0 \quad \text{cc } dE/dt \text{ partial} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{B} \quad \text{and} \quad d\mathbf{B}/dt \text{ partial} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{E} \quad ((11))$$

From ((11)) one may create standard wave-equations for $E\mathbf{i}$ and \mathbf{B} separately leading to $E\mathbf{i}$ and \mathbf{B} behaving as $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ or $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$.

$$\text{Then (setting } c=1\text{): } d/dt \text{ partial } (E\mathbf{i} + i\mathbf{B}) - \text{grad} \times (E\mathbf{i} + i\mathbf{B}) = 0 \quad ((12))$$

$$((12)) \text{ may be written as: } d/dt \text{ partial } (E\mathbf{i} + i\mathbf{B}) (i) + e_{jik} \text{ grad } (j) (E\mathbf{i} + i\mathbf{B}) (k) = 0 \quad ((13))$$

Here e_{jik} is the Levi-Civita symbol which may be thought of as a matrix labeled by j with entries ik . Thus, this matrix is dotted with the \mathbf{p} operator and represents the spin matrix, i.e. spin 1.

Conclusion

Both a photon and electron satisfy special relativistic equations, with the photon having $m_0=0$. Both are linked with $\exp(-iEt + i\mathbf{p}\cdot\mathbf{r})$ (again through special relativity), but it is the intrinsic force which differs. For a particle with rest mass, the intrinsic force is m_0 (inertia), while for a photon it is $E\mathbf{i}$ (the electric field). We suggest that in analyzing a particle, one wishes to have an equation

linear in the intrinsic force. This force is associated with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. The equation should indicate any geometry (due to rotational invariance etc) which exists. In the rest mass case, linearizing the Lorentz invariant $-EE + p \cdot p = -m^2$ suffices because the intrinsic force is m_0 . Part of the geometry is $p \cdot p$ (rotational invariance) which is linked with Pauli 2x2 matrices and so matrices linked to these appear upon linearization.

In the case of the photon, the intrinsic force is EI , the electric field. Momentum, which imparts an impulse on a target, is a consequence of the intrinsic force, i.e. momentum density = $1/c_0 E \times B$ (where B is the magnetic field). In the photon case, one does not have to linearize an equation like a Lorentz invariant or try to make arguments to justify $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$ arises as a solution for EI and B from Maxwell's equations with no sources. The intrinsic force EI is automatically linked with $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (i.e. the consequential force p). Secondly, Maxwell's equations allow one to immediately write an equation linear in EI and the presence of $\text{grad } x$ indicates geometry and leads to e_{ijk} as the spin matrix, i.e. spin 1 instead of spin $1/2$ for a rest mass in which case rest mass inertia is the intrinsic force.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Relation Between Special Relativity, Newtonian Mechanics and Simple Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2026)